

Electrochemical sensor for simultaneous determination of dextromethorphan hydrobromide and paracetamol at carbon paste electrode modified with synthesized indium tin oxide nanoparticles and ionic liquid

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Abstract : Indium tin oxide nanoparticles were synthesized by solution route using cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide as surfactant and used as a modifier of the electrode. An electrochemical study for simultaneous quantification of dextromethorphan hydrobromide (DXM) and paracetamol (PA) by adsorptive stripping differential pulse voltammetry at a carbon paste electrode modified with the composite of indium tin oxide nanoparticles and 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride ionic liquid (ITO-IL-CME) is described. Phosphate buffer (0.05 M) at pH 7 was found to be the ideal supporting electrolyte for the electrochemical study. The voltammetric results indicate that ITO-IL-CME remarkably enhances the electrocatalytic activity towards the oxidation of DXM and PA in neutral solution. The peak current increased linearly with the concentration for DXM in the range from 9.70×10^{-7} M to 6.20×10^{-4} M with a correlation coefficient of 0.989 and for PA with the concentration in the range from 3.62×10^{-8} M to 7.18×10^{-4} M with a correlation coefficient of 0.995. The detection limits for simultaneous determination of DXM and PA were 4.66×10^{-8} M and 8.40×10^{-9} M for DXM and PA respectively. The proposed procedure was successfully applied for determination of the drugs in pharmaceutical formulations, human serum and urine sample with good apparent recoveries without interference from matrix. The nanocomposite material modified carbon paste electrode has several advantages such as providing improved voltammetric behavior, long time stability, good selectivity, high sensitivity and excellent reproducibility.

Keywords : Dextromethorphan hydrobromide, paracetamol, 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride, indium tin oxide nanoparticles, modified carbon paste electrode, adsorptive stripping differential pulse voltammetry.

1. Introduction

Dextromethorphan hydrobromide (DXM, (+)-3-methoxy-17-methyl-(9 α , 13 α , 14 α)-morphinan hydrobromide) is an over the counter nonnarcotic antitussive drug. It acts through depression of the medullary centers of the brain to decrease the involuntary urge to cough. It affects the signals in the brain that trigger cough reflex. The drug is beneficial when administered in recommended doses. However, DXM produces a range of toxicities when consumed in high doses and can cause liver damage, heart attack, stroke, and death¹. Though DXM is a very effective safe-to-use medicament, abuse of the drug replicates alcohol like effect such as hallucination, paranoia, euphoria and suicidal tendency². Number of adolescents in the

United States and Europe intoxicate themselves with megadoses of DXM viz. 5 to 10 times the dose recommended for control of annoying nonproductive coughs. Over dosage of DXM lacks the ability to metabolize the drug normally, leading to rapid acute toxicity with profound psychological and physiological effects³. Also, interaction between DXM and other substances (e.g. alcohol, acetaminophen, 3,4-methylenedioxy methamphetamine and other over the counter cough medicines) produces a synergistic effect that can be very dangerous⁴. Several analytical methods have been employed for the determination of the DXM, like high performance liquid chromatography^{5,6}, micellar liquid chromatography⁷, RP-HPLC⁸, first-derivative spectrophotometry⁹, capillary gas chromatography¹⁰ and voltammetric techniques^{11,12}. With respect to the use

of voltammetric techniques, very few articles were reported for the quantification of DXM with rare usage of modified electrodes¹³.

Paracetamol or *N*-acetyl-*p*-aminophenol (PA) is the most widely antipyretic, analgesic drug. It relieves pain and fever. Generally, limited use of paracetamol is safe and has no harmful side effects. However, overdose or long-term use of it may cause adverse effects on health because of the accumulation of toxic metabolites, which can lead to severe and sometimes fatal hepatotoxicity and nephrotoxicity¹⁴. PA is also combined with other active ingredients in prescription medicines that treat allergy, cough, colds, flu, and sleeplessness. Varieties of methods have been used for the determination of PA in pharmaceutical preparations and human plasma like reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography¹⁵, RP-UPLC¹⁶, spectrophotometry^{17,18}, flow-injection analysis¹⁹ and voltammetric techniques²⁰. PA is present in some pharmaceutical preparations containing DXM in order to achieve synergistic effect as a combinational drug, though with different mechanisms of action²¹. The presence of analgesic and cough suppressant in a pharmaceutical formulations work together in the brain to decrease pain and reduce the cough reflex.

Ionic liquids (IL) are salts those are liquid at or above room temperature. They possess several advantages (e.g. high intrinsic conductivity, wide electrochemical windows, low volatility, high thermal stability and good solvating ability). Higher currents (both faradaic and capacitive) are often observed at ionic liquid-carbon paste composite electrode (IL-CME) compared to traditional bare carbon paste electrode due to its larger electro-active surface area promoting increase in electron transfer at the electrode surface²².

Voltammetric methods of analysis have been receiving considerable attention since past few decades due to their simplicity, efficiency and low cost. Modification of carbon paste working electrode surface imparts high sensitivity and selectivity to the analyte response²³. Use of nanoparticles as chemically modified electrodes for electroanalysis of drugs, has enhanced the scope and analytical applicability of the technique in the field of drug analysis²⁴.

In view of medical and pharmacological importance, as well as increasing trend of DXM abuse with potential increase in toxicity of combined drug formulations of DXM and PA on over dosage, there is a compelling need to develop reliable, selective and sensitive analytical method for simultaneous quantification of DXM and PA in pharmaceutical products and in human body fluids. However, to the best of our knowledge, only few reports on voltammetric method have been reported for the simultaneous determination of DXM and PA compound²⁵. Therefore, the objective of the present study is to develop an electrochemical sensor for the simultaneous determination of DXM and PA, to understand the electrochemical reaction mechanisms and to determine their diffusion coefficients in solution. Further, it aims to determine simultaneously the level of concentration of DXM and PA in pharmaceutical and clinical preparations in presence of preservatives and excipients with the developed sensor.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Chemicals

All chemicals were of analytical grade and were used without further purification. Graphite powder (amorphous graphite size, < 50 μm) was purchased from S.D. Fine Chemicals and mineral oil was from Fluka. Indium chloride ($\text{InCl}_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$), tin chloride pentahydrate ($\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$), ammonium hydroxide, ethanol, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), DXM, PA and 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride ionic liquid (IL) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Britton-Robinson buffer (BR) solution 0.04 *M* was used to investigate pH dependence of DXM and PA. Other buffer solutions used were phosphate ($\text{K}_2\text{HPO}_4/\text{KH}_2\text{PO}_4$ -Phos), tris(hydroxymethyl)amino methane (Tris) and 4-(2-hydroxy ethyl)-1-piperazine ethane sulphonic acid (HEPES). Double distilled water was used for the preparation of aqueous solutions. Tablets/syrup/lozenges of DXM and tablets/syrup of PA available from local pharmacies were subjected to analysis.

2.2. Instrumentation

Voltammetry measurements and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) study have been per-

formed on Eco Chemie, Electrochemical Work Station, model Autolab PGSTAT 30 using GPES software version 4.9005 and Frequency Response Analyser, software version 2.0 respectively. A three electrode system employing an Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) and platinum electrode were used as reference and counter electrodes respectively. Bare carbon paste electrode (CPE)/synthesized indium tin oxide nanoparticles modified carbon paste electrode (ITO)/1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride ionic liquid modified carbon paste electrode (IL-CME)/synthesized indium tin oxide nanoparticles with 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride ionic liquid composite modified carbon paste electrode (ITO-IL-CME) were used as working electrodes. The EIS studies were performed in the frequency range from 10^{-1} to 10^5 Hz at open circuit potential. The pH measurements were performed using an ELICO LI 120 pH meter. Conductivity measurement was carried out using four point probe instrument, Scientific Equipment, Roorkee. The energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDAX) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) measurements were recorded using FEI Quanta-250 model, Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were registered by FEI TF 30 model, Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD, Rigaku, D/Max-RA, Cu K α) and Perkin-Elmer FTIR spectrophotometer version 10.03.07 in wave range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} were used for characterization of synthesized indium tin oxide nanoparticles.

2.3. Synthesis of indium tin oxide nanoparticles

A mixture of 1.105 g of $\text{InCl}_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.21 g of $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was dissolved in water and 20 mL ethanol was added followed by adding 0.05 g of CTAB surfactant and drop by drop addition of ammonia solution under constant stirring at ambient condition. The whole mixture was stirred for 1 h on magnetic stirrer. It was then transferred to an autoclave and heated at 150 °C for 5 h. The product was centrifuged and washed with de-ionized water and further by ethanol. Pale blue coloured nanocrystalline indium tin oxide was obtained after the dried product was subjected to heat treatment at 400 °C for 3 h in muffle furnace.

2.4. Preparation of CPE, ITO-CME, IL-CME and ITO-IL-CME

CPE was prepared by mixing graphite with mineral oil at composition 70 : 30 (w/w) using a motor and pestle and was homogenized for 30 min. ITO-CME, IL-CME and ITO-ILCME were prepared by mixing graphite powder, indium tin oxide nanoparticles and/or 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride, mineral oil with various weight ratios. The pastes were then packed into a Teflon micro tip (diameter 0.5 mm) and a copper wire was inserted into the paste to establish an electrical contact. A new surface was regenerated by pressing out an excess of paste out of the tip and polishing it against zero grade butter paper.

2.5. Voltammetry procedure – Determination of DXM and PA

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) and differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) studies were carried out with appropriate quantity of the DXM and/or PA with pH 7 phosphate buffer (Phos). The solution was then transferred into an electrochemical cell and the measurements were carried out at 25 ± 0.2 °C. N_2 gas purging was not required as oxygen did not interfere in the measurements. The cyclic voltammetric experiments were carried out by sweeping the potential between +0.65 to +1.25 V for DXM and between +0.15 to 0.75 V. For simultaneous recording of DPVs for DXM and PA, the potential range were within +0.20 to +1.1 V.

2.6. Sample treatment for scanning electron microscope (SEM) and transmission electron microscope (TEM) analysis

Morphology studies of ITO were carried out by SEM and TEM. Samples of ITO for TEM measurements were prepared by placing drops of the solution (sample in alcohol) on coated Cu grids and subsequently drying in air. For SEM analysis, ITO nanoparticles were sonicated in toluene, allowed to dry and then employed for analysis.

2.7. Sample preparation – Standard and real sample

The pharmaceutical preparations were Alkox-Dx (Alkem Laboratories Ltd.) and Asciril-D (Glenmark

Pharmaceuticals Ltd.) cough syrups each containing 10 mg of dextromethrophan hydrobromide per 5 mL, TusQ-D lozenges (Blue Cross Laboratories Ltd.) containing 5 mg of dextromethrophan hydro-bromide, P-250 (Apex Laboratories Ltd.) containing 250 mg of paracetamol, Pyrigesic (East India Pharmaceutical Works Ltd.) containing 500 mg paracetamol and Alex-P⁺ (Glenmark Pharmaceuticals Ltd.) containing 5 mg of dextromethrophan hydrobromide and 170 mg of paracetamol per 5 mL.

Five tablets/lozenges were accurately weighed and finely powdered with a mortar and pestle. To a corresponding weight of the real sample water was added, filtered through a Qualigens (615) filter paper into a 100 mL calibrated flask. The residue was washed several times with water and the solution was diluted to the mark. Appropriate volume of this solution was diluted to 25 mL with phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) and then transferred to an electrolytic cell for the determination of DXM and/or PA.

To 1 mL of blood serum/urine/syrup, supporting electrolyte was added and made up to 10 mL and analyzed. Standard addition method was employed for quantification of DXM and PA as individual/combinations in pharmaceutical preparations, blood serum and urine samples.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of indium tin oxide nanoparticles

3.1.1. X-Ray diffraction studies (XRD) of synthesized indium tin oxide nanoparticles

The XRD of indium tin oxide is given in Fig. 1. All diffractions can be indexed as cubic crystal structure of indium oxide. Indium oxide nanoparticles exhibits the reflection from the (222) planes as the most predominant peak in the X-ray diffraction pattern. Tin atoms are doped into the indium oxide lattice since no evidence of characteristic peaks of Sn, SnO or SnO₂ were indicated in the spectra. The peaks in the diffraction spectrum are found to be sharp indicating highly crystalline nature of the nanoparticles. No characteristic peaks of impurities were detected.

Table 1 shows that all the peaks can be perfectly indexed to crystalline indium oxide, not only in their peak positions, but also in their relative intensities.

Using Debye-Scherrer's formula, the crystallite size, D_{hkl} is given by

$$D_{hkl} = K\lambda/\beta \cos\theta \quad (1)$$

where the Scherrer's constant K is taken to be 0.9, ' λ ' is the wavelength of X-ray (1.5406 Å), ' β ' is the full

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of indium tin oxide nanoparticles.

Table 1. XRD data for indium tin oxide nanoparticles

XRD data-d (nm)	4.130	2.924	2.532	1.986	1.789	1.526
Theoretical values-d (nm)	4.130	2.921	2.529	1.984	1.788	1.525
Crystalline plane (hkl)	211	222	400	431	440	622

width at half maximum of the peak, ' θ ', the Bragg angle and ' D ' is the particle diameter size. The mean particle diameter of ITO nanoparticles was found to be 30 nm.

3.1.2. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) of synthesized indium tin oxide nanoparticles

The morphology and micro-structure of ITO were investigated by SEM and TEM. Fig. 2(A) is the SEM image of synthesized indium tin oxide nanoparticles,

which is observed to be non-agglomerated with uniform morphology and of cubic shape. The chemical constituent of particles was analyzed by EDAX (Fig. 2(B)). The In L α 1 (3.286 keV) and Sn L α 1 (3.443 keV) peaks show the presence of indium and tin elements with the atomic molar percent determined for indium being 91% and for tin 9% in the lattice of the ITO nanoparticles.

The TEM image of synthesized indium tin oxide nanoparticles is given in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2. SEM image of (A) ITO nanoparticles and (B) Energy-dispersive X-ray spectrum for ITO nanoparticles.

Fig. 3. TEM image of ITO nanoparticles.

The TEM examination of synthesized ITO indicates that the morphology is homogeneous showing a cubic structure.

3.1.3. FTIR spectral analysis of synthesized indium tin oxide nanoparticles

The peaks at 476, 557, 593 and 849 cm^{-1} in Fig. 4 show the characteristic bands of crystalline In_2O_3 . The observed bands at 476 and 557 cm^{-1} are attributed to the stretching vibrations of In-O whereas bands at 593 and 849 cm^{-1} are characteristic of In-O bending vibrations. The vibrations extending from 2328 and 1293 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of hydrogen bonds involved in O-H oscillations arising from adsorbed water²⁶.

3.1.4. Conductivity measurements of synthesized indium tin oxide nanoparticles

Electrical conductivity measurement of synthesized indium tin oxide nanoparticles was performed using the DC four-point probe technique²⁷ on synthesized

Fig. 4. FT-IR spectrum of indium tin oxide nanoparticles.

ITO pellets (1.7 cm diameter, 0.42 mm thickness). Three pellets were prepared by pressing about 100 mg of synthesized ITO with an IR pressing tool. Sheet resistance ' R_s ' across the pellets was determined to be $2.41 \times 10^{-2} \Omega/\text{sq}$, the value of the average electrical conductivity ' σ ' calculated from R_s obtained was 98.79 S cm^{-1} .

3.2. Effect of pH

The effect of pH on peak current and peak potential for DXM ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$) and PA ($2.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$) are shown in Fig. 5(A) and (B) respectively in BR buffer from pH 2 to 10 at CPE using differential pulse voltammetry.

It is observed that the peak current of DXM increases till pH 7.0 followed by a decrease with further increase in pH. Similarly for PA, the maximum peak current is obtained at pH 7.0. Therefore, pH 7 was selected for the determination of DXM and PA in their mixture. The peak potentials for the oxidation of DXM and PA is shifted negatively with increasing pH, indicating that protons take part in the electrochemical reaction processes for both the molecules. A slope of -0.052 V/pH and -0.050 V/pH for DXM and PA were observed respectively, suggesting that same number of electrons and protons were involved for their electro-oxidation. The effects of several supporting electrolytes (0.1 M) viz. HEPES, phosphate ($\text{KH}_2\text{PO}_4 + \text{K}_2\text{HPO}_4$), Tris and BR buffer at pH 7 for DXM ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$) and PA ($2.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$) on peak current were tested as shown in Fig. 6.

Of these, phosphate buffer (Phos) gave the best response in terms of peak height and the peak shape. Optimization of buffer concentration was carried out by varying phosphate concentration in the range from 0.01 M to 0.2 M, the best peak response was observed for 0.05 M of Phos (pH 7) and hence was used for further studies.

3.3. Effect of surface modification and optimization of the amount of the modifier

The cyclic voltammograms for DXM ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$) and PA ($2.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$) in 0.05 M of Phos (pH 7) at

Fig. 5. DPV plot of (A) I_p vs pH () and E_p vs pH () for $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ DXM and (B) I_p vs pH () and E_p vs pH () for $2.5 \times 10^{-6} M$ PA at CPE.

CPE, ITO-CME, IL-CME and ITO-IL-CME is shown in Fig. 7(A) and (B). It is seen that DXM and PA show irreversible peaks. It was evident from the figures that the modification of the CPE with indium tin oxide and ionic liquid enlarged the peak current considerably by about 2.5 and 3 times for DXM and PA respectively, indicating that the surface property of the modified electrode has been significantly changed due to synergistic effect of ITO with IL.

The influence on the amount of ITO nanoparticles

Fig. 6. Effect of supporting electrolytes (pH 7.0) on anodic peak current of $1.00 \times 10^{-5} M$ DXM and $2.5 \times 10^{-6} M$ PA at CPE.

and IL added to CPE was studied for a solution containing DXM ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$) and PA ($2.5 \times 10^{-6} M$) in pH 7 by DPV. Table 2 shows the weight ratios for the various modified electrode. The peak current increased with increase in the percentage weight of nanoparticles till the ratio of composition (w/w) for graphite : ITO nanoparticles : IL : mineral oil was 45 : 20 : 05 : 30

The DPV peaks are well-resolved for PA and DXM at ITO-IL-CME with the peak potentials at about 0.391 V and 0.872 V respectively. The separation of peak potentials is 0.481 V for PA-DXM which is large enough to determine PA and DXM simultaneously.

The surface areas for CPE, IL-CME, ITO-CME and ITO-IL-CME having same bore size using 6 mM mixture of $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ system in 0.1 N KNO_3 by cyclic voltammetric technique was calculated from Randles-Sevcik equation²⁸. It was found to be 0.00958, 0.0175, 0.0345 and 0.0847 cm^2 respectively.

3.4. Cyclic voltammetry

The effect of scan rate to investigate electrode reaction mechanism is studied and are shown in Fig. 8(A) and (B) for DXM ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$) and PA ($2.5 \times 10^{-6} M$) at ITO-IL-CME in 0.05 M phosphate (pH 7)

Fig. 7. Cyclic voltammograms for oxidation of (A) of $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ DXM at; (a) CPE (—), (b) IL-CME (—), (c) ITO-CME (—), (d) ITO-IL-CME (—) vs Ag/AgCl and (B) of $2.5 \times 10^{-6} M$ PA at; (a) CPE (—), (b) IL-CME (—), (c) ITO-CME (—), (d) ITO-IL-CME (—) vs Ag/AgCl in 0.05 M Phos (pH 7); scan rate 100 mV/s at 25 °C.

Table 2. Composition of modified electrodes with various weight ratios of graphite : ITO : IL : mineral oil

Electrode	Graphite (mg)	Indium tin oxide nanoparticles (mg)	1-Butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride ionic liquid	Mineral oil (mg)
ITO-CME	65	5	—	30
IL-CME	65	—	5	30
ITO-IL-CME 1	60	5	5	30
ITO-IL-CME 2	55	10	5	30
ITO-IL-CME 3	50	15	5	30
ITO-IL-CME 4	45	20	5	30
(ITO-IL-CME)				
ITO-IL-CME 5	40	25	5	30
ITO-IL-CME 6	40	20	10	30
ITO-IL-CME 7	35	20	5	30
ITO-IL-CME 8	52	8	10	30

respectively. The scan rates were from 50 to 900 mV s⁻¹.

The peak current varied linearly with increase in the scan rate for DXM (Fig. 9(A)) and PA (Fig. 10(A)) with regression equation

$$I_p = 4.216 + 0.035 v$$

$$[R^2 = 0.984; I_p : \mu A, v : (mV/s)] \quad (2)$$

$$I_p = 3.442 + 0.033 v$$

$$[R^2 = 0.995; I_p : \mu A, v : (mV/s)] \quad (3)$$

respectively, validating a typical adsorption-controlled

process. A plot of $\log I_p$ against $\log v$ for $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ DXM (Fig. 9(B)) and for $2.5 \times 10^{-6} M$ PA (Fig. 10(B)) was linear with a slope of 0.666 and 0.941 indicating that the electrode process is adsorption controlled.

Also, the peak potential shifted to more positive values with the increase of scan rate, which confirmed the irreversibility of the oxidation process for both the molecules (Figs. 9(C) and 10(C)).

For an irreversible reaction the number of electrons (n) involved in the oxidation reaction was calcu-

Fig. 8. Cyclic voltammograms for the oxidation of (A) $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ DXM, (B) $2.5 \times 10^{-6} M$ PA : for scan rate (a) 50, (b) 100, (c) 200, (d) 300, (e) 500, (f) 600, (g) 700, (h) 800, (i) 900 mV s^{-1} in $0.05 M$ Phos (pH 7) at ITO-IL-CME vs Ag/AgCl at 25°C .

Fig. 9. Plot of (A) I_p vs v , (B) $\log I_p$ vs $\log v$, (C) $\log E_p$ vs v , for $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ DXM in $0.05 M$ Phos (pH 7) at ITO-IL-CME vs Ag/AgCl at 25°C .

lated from the following equation²⁹ :

$$E_p - E_p/2 = 47.7/n\alpha \text{ [mV at } 25^\circ \text{C]} \quad (4)$$

$E_p - E_p/2$ value for DXM and PA was found to be 75 mV and 55 mV respectively. On substitution in the above equation and assuming α as 0.5, 'n' was calculated was found to be 1.2 for DXM i.e. approximately one proton is transferred and 1.7 for PA i.e. approximately two proton is transferred in the oxidation process. Since the oxidation occurred by transfer of the same number of electrons and protons for both the molecules, the oxidation of DXM is an one electron one proton process and for PA it is two electron two

proton process at the ITO-IL-CME electrode.

Scheme 1(a) and (b) show the probable electrochemical reaction process for the oxidation of DXM and PA at the ITO-IL-CME.

In order to calculate the electron transfer rate constant the following Laviron's equation was used

$$E_p = E^0 + \frac{RT}{\alpha nF} \ln \frac{RTk^0}{\alpha nF} + \frac{RT}{\alpha nF} \ln v \quad (5)$$

where, k^0 is the electron transfer rate constant, α is the electron transfer coefficient, v is the scan rate, n is the electron transfer number and E^0 is the formal po-

Fig. 10. Plot of (A) I_p vs v , (B) $\log I_p$ vs $\log v$, (C) E_p vs v for $2.5 \times 10^{-6} M$ PA in $0.05 M$ Phos (pH 7) at ITO-IL-CME vs Ag/AgCl at $25^\circ C$.

Scheme 1(a). Electro-oxidative mechanism for dextromethorphan hydrobromide.

Scheme 1(b). Electro-oxidative mechanism for paracetamol.

tential. k^0 can be determined from the intercept and slope of the linear plot of E_p vs $\log v$. E^0 can be deduced from the intercept of E_p vs v plot. The values

of k^0 were determined to be $330.0 s^{-1}$ and $380.3 s^{-1}$ for DXM and PA respectively. Large values obtained for electron transfer rate constant indicate high ability of promoting electrons between the molecules and the ITO-IL-CME electrode surface.

3.5. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS)

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) is a simple and effective way to measure the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) of the electrochemical reactions²⁹. The EIS measurements were performed for DXM ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$) and PA ($2.5 \times 10^{-6} M$), in a phosphate buffer solution pH 7 at CPE, IL-CME, ITO-CME and

Fig. 11. Nyquist plots for the EIS measurements for (A) $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ DXM at (a) CPE (), (b) IL-CME (◆◆◆◆), (c) ITO-CME (), (d) ITO-IL-CME (○○○○); (B) for $2.5 \times 10^{-6} M$ PA at (a) CPE (), (b) IL-CME (××××), (c) ITO-CME (◆◆◆◆), (d) ITO-IL-CME (●●●●) in the frequency range from 10^{-1} to 10^5 Hz, the inset shows an equivalent circuit was used for data fitting.

ITO-IL-CME. It can be seen from Fig. 11(A) and (B) that each spectrum exhibited a semicircular and a linear portion.

The semicircle corresponds to the charge transfer process at the electrode at a high frequency range, whereas the linear portion in the spectra is due to the diffusion process in the low frequency range. The diameter of the semicircle represents the magnitude of R_{ct} at the electrode surface. The measured EIS data were fitted with an equivalent circuit known as the Randles equivalent circuit, consisting of ohmic resistance (R_s) of the electrolyte solution, the double layer capacitance (C_{dl}), electron transfer resistance (R_{ct}) and the Warburg impedance (Z_w) resulting from the diffusion of ions from the bulk of the electrolyte to the interface. The values of R_{ct} at CPE, IL-CME, ITO-CME and ITO-IL-CME were 518.9Ω , 299.3Ω , 238.5Ω and 208.4Ω , for DXM and 317.0Ω , 295.6Ω , 286.5Ω and 235.1Ω , for PA respectively. By comparing the data obtained, the R_{ct} for CPE is much higher than at ITO-IL-CME for both the molecules implying that the charge transfer process is relatively fast at ITO-IL-CME compared to CPE.

3.6. Chronocoulometry (CC)

Chronocoulometry is a controlled-potential technique in which the measurement of charge as a function of

time is observed. Application of this technique helps to study of electrode kinetics by, determining the diffusion coefficient of the analyte in solution and by determining the surface coverage area of the electrode the extent of the adsorption of the analyte on the electrode can be ascertained³⁰. Double-potential step chronocoulometry permits an “*in situ*” double layer correction even in the presence of extensive adsorption. The above technique was applied individually for $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ DXM and $2.5 \times 10^{-6} M$ PA in $0.05 M$ phosphate (pH 7).

From following equation²⁹ :

$$Q_t = (2nFD^{1/2} CA t^{1/2}) / \pi^{1/2} + nFA \Gamma^0 + Q_{dl} \quad (6)$$

the Anson plot of total charge (Q_t) in coulombs vs the square root of time ($t^{1/2}$) in seconds should give a linear relationship. Q_{dl} is the double layer charge in Coulombs, n is the number of electrons, F is the Faradays constant ($96485 C$), C is the concentration in mol/cm^3 , A is the area of the electrode in cm^2 , Γ^0 is surface coverage in mol cm^{-2} and D is the diffusion coefficient in $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$. The diffusion coefficient and surface coverage were estimated from the slope and intercept of the Ansons plot at CPE, IL-CME, ITO-CME and ITO-IL-CME as given in Table 3.

Table 3. Chronocoulometry of 1.0×10^{-5} M DXM and 2.5×10^{-6} M PA in 0.05 M Phos (pH 7)

Molecule	Electrode	Slope ($\mu\text{C s}^{-1/2}$)	Intercept Q_{ads} (μC)	Surface coverage (10^{-10} mol cm^{-2})	Diffusion coefficient ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)
DXM	CPE	0.367 ± 2.14	0.528 ± 1.79	5.71	1.23×10^{-3}
	IL	0.945 ± 3.48	1.280 ± 0.92	7.59	2.45×10^{-3}
	ITO	2.510 ± 3.79	3.260 ± 2.13	9.78	4.45×10^{-3}
	ITO-IL-CME	7.830 ± 1.81	8.990 ± 4.07	10.99	7.19×10^{-3}
PA	CPE	0.113 ± 3.55	7.050 ± 3.77	38.1	4.68×10^{-4}
	IL	0.245 ± 2.19	16.10 ± 2.84	47.6	6.58×10^{-4}
	ITO	0.574 ± 1.03	42.40 ± 1.62	63.7	9.32×10^{-4}
	ITO-IL-CME	1.53 ± 3.13	160.9 ± 2.20	98.4	10.92×10^{-4}

The values of D and Γ^0 are found to increase from CPE to ITO-IL-CME indicating that maximum accumulation of DXM or PA on ITO-IL-CME from among all the electrodes studied.

3.7. Adsorptive stripping differential pulse voltammetry (AdSDPV)

3.7.1. Effect of accumulation parameters – Accumulation potential and accumulation time

AdSDPV was employed to study the influence of differential pulse anodic stripping peak current for 1.0×10^{-5} M DXM and 2.5×10^{-6} M PA on the accumulation potential (E_{acc}) and accumulation time (t_{acc}) at ITO-IL-CME in 0.05 M Phos buffer solution (pH

7). E_{acc} was determined by employing a potential widow from -1.0 V to 0.7 V. The peak current remained almost constant when the potential was positive from 0 V to 0.7 V for both the molecules. The peak current gradually increased as E_{acc} became negative and reached its maximum at -0.3 V and -0.50 V for DXM and PA respectively (Fig. 12(A)).

When potential shifts still further in the negative direction, there is drop in peak current with increase in the background current. Thus the optimum accumulation potential of -0.50 V was used for subsequent sensitive simultaneous determination of DXM and PA.

At the same accumulation potential, the effect of accumulation time on the efficiency of drugs onto the

Fig. 12. Influence of (A) accumulation potential and (B) accumulation time on the oxidation peak current of 1.0×10^{-5} M DXM and 2.5×10^{-6} M PA in 0.05 M Phos (pH 7.0) at ITO-IL-CME vs Ag/AgCl at 25°C .

working electrode surface was evaluated over a time range from 0.0 s to 150 s (Fig. 12(B)). Peak current increased very rapidly with increasing accumulation time, which induced rapid adsorption of DXM and PA on the surface of the modified electrode. A steady enhancement in the peak current was observed over the range from 0.0 s to 90 s for DXM and from 0.0 s to 110 s for PA and thereafter the peak intensity gradually scales off at longer accumulation time. This indicates that, further increase of accumulation time did not increase the response of DXM and PA on the electrode surface due to a complete coverage of electrode surface. Therefore, the accumulation time was fixed at 110 s with an optimal stirring rate of 1200 rpm for the analysis.

3.7.2. Effect of potential sweep parameters

To improve the sensitivity of adsorptive stripping differential pulse voltammetry for the simultaneous determination of 1.0×10^{-5} M DXM and 2.5×10^{-6} M PA at ITO-IL-CME, the effect of pulse amplitude, scan rate and pulse width on peak current were investigated. It was found that the peak currents increased significantly with increasing pulse amplitude from 10 to 50 mV and then almost remained constant from 60 mV to 100 mV. The pulse amplitude chosen for prac-

Table 4. Optimal parameters for determination of DXM and PA simultaneously by AdSDPV technique

Parameter	AdSDPV
pH	7
Supporting electrolyte	0.05 M Phosphate buffer
Accumulation potential	-0.5 V
Accumulation time	90 s
Stirring rate	1200 rpm
Pulse amplitude	50 mV
Pulse width	0.05 s
Scan rate	50 mV s ⁻¹

tical purpose was 50 mV. Faster scan rates resulted in higher peak currents but background currents also increased. Taking peak current and background current into consideration the scan rate chosen was 50 mV s⁻¹. The optimum pulse width was 0.05 s.

3.8. Determination of DXM and PA by adsorptive stripping differential pulse voltammetry (AdSDPV)

Based on the optimal operating conditions (Table 4), AdSDPV measurements were undertaken in solutions containing different concentrations of DXM and PA individually and simultaneously.

Fig. 13(A) and (B) are the voltammograms of DXM and PA respectively carried out individually.

For simultaneous determination, two separate sets

Fig. 13. AdSDPV curves obtained at ITO-IL-CME for (A) DXM at different concentrations (a) 0.6, (b) 0.8, (c) 6.0, (d) 8.0, (e) 60.0, (f) 80.0, (g) 150, (h) 300, (i) 500, (j) 700 μ M. (B) PA at different concentrations (a) 0.4, (b) 0.8, (c) 2.0, (d) 8.0, (e) 40.0, (f) 60.0, (g) 80.0, (h) 200.0, (i) 400.0, (j) 600.0 μ M; scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹ in 0.05 M Phos (pH 7.0); pulse amplitude 50 mV. Inset of (A) and (B) shows the linearity graph of DXM and PA respectively.

of experiments were carried out. In the first instance, concentration of DXM was increased in the presence of fixed concentrations of PA and the voltammograms were recorded (Fig. 14(A)) and vice versa as given in Fig. 14(B). For the second instance, both DXM and PA were determined by simultaneously increasing their concentrations as given in Fig. 14(C). The linear working range (LWR), empirical limits of detection (LOD) ($S/N = 3$), linear regression equation (LRE) and correlation coefficient (r) were determined (Table 5).

The anodic peak current corresponding to the oxidation of DXM and PA correlates linearly with its concentration in the entire range of investigation.

From Table 5 it is observed that the LWR and LOD determined for DXM and PA simultaneously are in good agreement with when both were individually determined.

Table 6 shows a comparison of the proposed sensor with the reported electrochemical sensors for the determination of DXM and PA individually and simultaneously.

3.9. Validation and interference studies

The precision of the developed method was investigated with respect to both repeatability (single electrode), reproducibility (multiple electrodes), rugged-

Fig. 14. AdSDPV curves obtained at ITO-IL-CME for (A) DXM at different concentrations (a) 0.8, (b) 4.0, (c) 20.0, (d) 40.0, (e) 60.0, (f) 80.0, (g) 100, (h) 200 μM in the presence of $2.5 \times 10^{-6} M$ of PA. (B) PA at different concentrations (a) 0.2, (b) 0.6, (c) 0.8, (d) 40.0, (e) 60.0, (f) 80.0, (g) 200.0, (h) 200.0, (i) 400.0, (j) 600.0, (k) 800.0 μM in the presence of $1.00 \times 10^{-6} M$ DXM. (C) Simultaneous determination of DXM and PA at different concentrations (a) 0.2 and 0.2, (b) 0.4 and 0.4, (c) 0.8 and 6.0, (d) 10.0 and 8.0, (e) 20.0 and 20.0, (f) 60.0 and 40.0, (g) 80.0 and 80.0, (h) 100.0 and 200.0, (i) 300.0 and 500.0, (j) 600.0 and 400.0 μM respectively in 0.05 M Phos (pH 7.0); scan rate 50 mV s^{-1} ; pulse amplitude 50 mV.

Table 5. Analytical parameters for electrochemical determination of DXM and/or PA in 0.05 M phosphate buffer (pH 7)

Molecule	LOD	% RSD	LWR	LRE	<i>r</i>
Parameters for individual molecule					
DXM	2.61×10^{-8}	2.34	8.00×10^{-7}	$I_p (\mu\text{A}) = 0.010 (\mu\text{M}) + 0.049$	0.998
			to		
			8.00×10^{-4}		
PA	1.58×10^{-9}	3.29	4.00×10^{-8}	$I_p (\mu\text{A}) = 0.030 (\mu\text{M}) + 0.349$	0.998
			to		
			8.00×10^{-4}		
Parameters when DXM concentration increases and PA concentration (2.5×10^{-6} M) remains constant					
DXM	1.58×10^{-8}	1.65	6.00×10^{-7}	$I_p (\mu\text{A}) = 0.017 (\mu\text{M}) + 0.788$	0.989
			to		
			7.00×10^{-4}		
Parameters data when PA concentration increases and DXM concentration (1.00×10^{-5} M) remains constant					
PA	1.45×10^{-9}	2.81	2.00×10^{-8}	$I_p (\mu\text{A}) = 0.091 (\mu\text{M}) + 0.350$	0.996
			to		
			7.40×10^{-4}		
Parameters when DXM and PA increases in concentration simultaneously					
DXM	4.66×10^{-8}	3.96	9.70×10^{-7}	$I_p (\mu\text{A}) = 0.076 (\mu\text{M}) + 3.505$	0.989
			to		
			6.20×10^{-4}		
PA	8.40×10^{-9}	2.87	3.62×10^{-8}	$I_p (\mu\text{A}) = 0.357 (\mu\text{M}) + 8.137$	0.995
			to		
			7.18×10^{-4}		

ness and interferences with standard solution of 1.0×10^{-4} M DXM and 1.0×10^{-5} M PA in 0.05 M Phosphate buffer solution (pH 7) at ITO-IL-CME. Repeatability was assessed by continuous electrooxidative determination of the standard solution with the same ITO-IL-CME electrode for 10 analyses. The anodic current decreased by 1.05% and 1.32% with the RSD value of 1.75% and 2.19% for DXM and PA respectively after completing 10 scans, which showed that the electrode responds with good repeatability. Reproducibility was investigated by determination of three replicate samples containing standard solution of DXM and PA on five consecutive days using multiple electrodes where the mean concentrations were found to be 1.09×10^{-4} M and 0.983×10^{-5} M with associated RSD values of 1.19% and 3.67% respectively. The ruggedness of the method was assessed by comparison of the intra- and inter-day assay results for DXM and PA that had been performed by two analysts. The RSD

values for intra- and inter-day assays of analyses performed in the same laboratory by two different analysts did not exceed 3.5%, thereby indicating the ruggedness of the method. The influence of peak current on DXM and PA in presence of interferences that are commonly present in biological media and 4-aminophenol (metabolite of paracetamol) were investigated. Also, DXM and PA are formulated in different dosage forms in combinations with drugs like aspirin, caffeine, phenylephrine, ascorbic acid and cetirizine dihydrochloride, therefore the extent of their interference along with DXM and PA were tested with the developed AdSDPV method. Under optimized experimental conditions, no effect on the determination of DXM and PA was observed up to 250-fold of Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , 200-fold of glucose and ascorbic acid, 150-fold of glucose and uric acid, 20-fold of citric acid, 100-fold of aspirin and caffeine,

Table 6. Comparison of the performances of electrochemical sensors for DXM and PA

Molecule	Modified electrode	Detection limit (<i>M</i>)	Linear range(<i>M</i>)	Refs.
Dextromethrophan hydrobromide	Carbon nanotubes-carbon microparticle-ionic liquid composite	8.81×10^{-6}	2.50×10^{-4} to 3.30×10^{-3}	11
	Reduced graphene oxide modified screen printed electrode after electromembrane extraction	1.50×10^{-6}	5.0×10^{-6} to 1.50×10^{-3}	12
	Hydrophilic carbon nanoparticles at the surface of carbon paste electrode	2.90×10^{-6}	8.0×10^{-6} to 8.0×10^{-4}	25
	ITO-IL-CME	2.61×10^{-8}	8.0×10^{-7} to 8.0×10^{-4}	This work
Paracetamol	Boron doped diamond electrode modified with Nafion and lead films	1.70×10^{-7}	5.0×10^{-7} to 2.0×10^{-4}	31
	Nafion/TiO ₂ – Graphene modified glassy carbon electrode	2.10×10^{-7}	4.0×10^{-6} to 2.0×10^{-5}	32
	Hydrophilic carbon nanoparticles at the surface of carbon paste electrode	1.50×10^{-8}	1.0×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-3}	25
	ITO-IL-CME	2.20×10^{-9}	4.0×10^{-8} to 6.0×10^{-4}	This work

Table 7. Assay of DXM and/or PA in pharmaceutical preparations (*n* = 5)

Dextromethrophan hydrobromide			Paracetamol		
Tablet/Syrup	Amount of drug in the sample (mg)	Amount of drug obtained in the proposed method (mg) ±RSD	Tablet/Syrup	Amount of drug in the sample (mg)	Amount of drug obtained in the proposed method (mg) ±RSD
Alex-P ⁺	5.0	4.8 ± 2.13	Alex-P ⁺	170.0	172.1 ± 1.17
Tus Q-D	5.0	5.1 ± 2.15	–	–	–
–	–	–	Pyrigesic	500.0	498.4 ± 2.94

60-fold of phenylepherine, 50-fold of cetirizine dihydrochloride and 70-fold of 4-aminophenol, indicating that the present modified electrode was highly selective towards the determination of DXM and PA.

3.10. Application to real matrices

Commercial pharmaceutical samples (tablets) containing DXM and/or PA present in tablets were analyzed in order to evaluate the practical applicability of

Table 8. Recovery test for DXM and/or PA in pharmaceutical, blood serum and urine samples ($n = 5$) by AdSDPV

	Dextromethorphan hydrobromide			Paracetamol		
	Std drug added $10^{-6} M$	Drug conc. $10^{-6} M$	Apparent recovery (%) $\pm RSD$	Std drug added $10^{-5} M$	Drug conc. $10^{-5} M$	Apparent recovery (%) $\pm RSD$
Alkox-Dx	–	3.54	–	–	–	–
	1.95	5.65	102.9 ± 2.14	–	–	–
	5.66	8.97	97.5 ± 1.333	–	–	–
	10.84	14.17	98.5 ± 1.75	–	–	–
Ascoril-D	–	8.24	–	–	–	–
	1.67	10.10	101.9 ± 1.48	–	–	–
	3.75	12.17	101.5 ± 3.15	–	–	–
	23.31	31.55	97.7 ± 2.66	–	–	–
P-250	–	–	–	–	1.12	–
	–	–	–	2.40	3.59	101.9 ± 1.24
	–	–	–	4.62	5.62	97.9 ± 2.91
	–	–	–	9.65	9.59	99.4 ± 2.68
Blood serum	–	ND	–	–	ND	–
	7.41	7.43	100.3 ± 1.39	1.18	1.21	102.5 ± 2.46
	10.70	10.8	100.8 ± 2.16	2.31	2.35	101.7 ± 2.93
	13.8	13.7	99.4 ± 2.94	3.40	3.51	103.2 ± 1.68
	21.9	21.7	99.2 ± 1.52	4.44	4.43	99.7 ± 3.35
Urine	–	ND	–	–	ND	–
	7.41	7.50	101.2 ± 2.44	3.31	3.35	101.2 ± 2.93
	16.70	16.40	98.4 ± 2.86	6.74	6.58	97.6 ± 3.14
	26.50	26.30	99.3 ± 1.13	11.90	11.72	98.5 ± 1.87

the developed method (Table 7). Recovery experiments on the spiked samples (tablets, blood and urine) were also carried out to evaluate matrix effects (Table 8). Standard solution additions yielded good average recoveries which ranged between 97.5% and 102.9% for DXM and 97.6% and 103.2% for PA indicating high reproducibility and reliability of the modified electrode.

4. Conclusion

The present work demonstrates a simple and sensitive electrochemical method for the simultaneous determination of dextromethorphan hydrobromide and paracetamol at carbon paste electrode modified with indium tin oxide and 1-buty-3-methylimidazolium chloride ionic liquid. Cyclic voltammetry and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy study results confirmed

the synergism of ITO nanoparticles and IL with unique catalytic activity at the electrode surface. Anodic stripping voltammetric technique was used for simultaneous determination of DXM and PA at ITO-IL-CME electrode and also was used for the first time. On comparison with unmodified carbon paste electrode and with some of the previously reported electrodes the ITO-IL-CME significantly enhanced the sensitivity, selectivity and reliability for individual and simultaneous determination of DXM and PA with low detection limits and large linear working range. The utilization of the developed sensor is an attempt to perform as a good alternative economically and environmental friendly for simultaneous determination of DXM and PA, in quality control of pharmaceutical formulations, testing of blood and urine samples in terms of easy handling, low cost and stability.

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References

1. M. D. V. Ziaee, E. A. Hamed, A. Hoshmand and K. Saam, *Int. J. Pharmacol.*, 2005, **1**, 293.
2. G. R. Hanson, P. J. Venturelli and A. Fleckenstein, "Drugs and Society", 9th ed., Jones & Bartlett Publishers, Massachusetts, 2006.
3. R. H. Schwartz, *Clin Pediatr (Phila)*, 2005, **44**, 565.
4. J. W. Cranston and R. Yoast, *Arch. Fam. Med.*, 1999, **8**, 99.
5. J. P. Rauha, H. Salornies and M. Aalto, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 1996, **15**, 287.
6. M. R. Louhaichia, S. Jebali, M. H. Loueslatia, N. Adhoum and L. Monser, *Talanta*, 2009, **78**, 991.
7. Martínez-Algaba, J. M. Bermúdez-Saldaña, R. M. Villanueva-Camanas, S. Sagrado and M. J. Medina-Hernández, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2006, **40**, 312.
8. H. Al-Akraa, N. Sarki and M. Alshehaby, *Int. J. Pharm. Pharm. Sci.*, 2013, **5**, 234.
9. V. Tantishaiyakul, C. Poeaknapo, P. Sribun and K. Sirisuppanon, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 1998, **17**, 237.
10. Y. J. Wu, Y. Y. Cheng, S. Zeng and M. M. Ma, *J. Chromatogr. (B)*, 2003, **784**, 219.
11. H. Heli, S. Majdi, A. Jabbari, N. Sattarahmady and A. A. Moosavi-Movahedi, *J. Solid State Electrochem.*, 2010, **14**, 1515.
12. A. R. Fakhari, M. H. K. Hamid Ahmar, A. Shahsavani and S. Kazemi Movahed, *Electroanalysis*, 2014, **26**, 521.
13. N. Thapliyal, H. Patel, R. Karpoornath, R. N. Goyal and R. Patel, *Talanta*, 2015, **142**, 157.
14. M. Mazer and J. Perrone, *J. Med. Toxicol.*, 2008, **4**, 2.
15. R. V. Rajan and M. N. Rajesh, *Pharmacia Sinica*, 2014, **5**, 34.
16. M. P. Sheetal and M. B. S. Yadav, *J. Chem. Pharma. Res.*, 2015, **7**, 1308.
17. L. R. Shivaji, L. R. Kailas and G. B. Vishwas, *Chem. Sci. Trans.*, 2015, **4**, 377.
18. B. Morelli, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 1989, **7**, 577.
19. S. S. Jessica, M. H. O. Rodrigo, R. M. Eduardo and M. A. Rodrigo, *J. Braz. Chem. Soc.*, 2014, **25**, 484.
20. B. J. Sanghavi and A. K. Srivastava, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2011, **706**, 246.
21. A. E. Olesen, C. Staahl, Z. Ali, A. M. Drewes and L. Arendt-Nielsen, *Basic Clin. Pharmacol. Toxicol.*, 2007, **101**, 172.
22. D. S. Silvester, *Analyst*, 2011, **136**, 4871.
23. P. B. Desai, R. M. Kotkar and A. K. Srivastava, *J. Solid State Electrochem.*, 2008, **12**, 1067.
24. M. P. Kingsley, P. B. Desai and A. K. Srivastava, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 2015, **741**, 71.
25. M. Amiri, F. Rezapour and A. Bezaatpour, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 2014, **735**, 10.
26. A. Ayeshamariam, M. Bououdina and C. Sanjeeviraja, *Mat. Sci. Semicon. Proc.*, 2013, **6**, 686.
27. Y. Singh, "Electrical Resistivity measurements : A Review", International Conference on Ceramics, Bikaner, India, International Journal of Modern Physics : Conference Series, World Scientific Publishing Company, 2013, **22**, pp. 745-756.
28. J. Wang, "Analytical Electro Chemistry", 2nd ed., Wiley-VCH, New York, 2001.
29. A. J. Bard and L. R. Faulkner, "Electrochemical Methods – Fundamentals and Applications", 2nd ed., John Wiley & Sons, New York, 2001.
30. R. A. Osteryoung, G. Lauer and F. C. Anson, *J. Chem. Edu.*, 1983, **60**, 290.
31. K. Tyszczyk-Rotko *et al.*, *Talanta*, 2014, **129**, 384.
32. Y. Fan, J. H. Liu, H. T. Lu and Q. Zhang, *Colloid Surf. B : Biointerface*, 2011, **85**, 289.